

Risks In Sports Success In Psychological And Social Terms

Risk Factors In Sports

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To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-11, 2024, p. 46– 103. - 0099-0001-2411-0314.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE")

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

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Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

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Abstract

Athletes engage in their activity daily, facing several hazards. Although some dangers adversely impact athletic performance, others result in sports injuries. Numerous dangers are encountered or considered throughout training, but they become evident when they result in diminished performance and harm. When these and analogous hazards materialize, it is too late, resulting in either diminished performance or harm for the athlete. We shall assess the internal and external components that comprise risk factors in sports. We provide a taxonomy of environmental elements, referred to as external factors, and human characteristics, termed internal factors. We shall endeavor to elucidate the subjects under the categories included in

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THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

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this categorization in more depth within the scope of our expertise. The risk themes are located at the conclusion of the subsequent section, where the sources used and internal considerations are elaborated upon comprehensively.

Keywords: *Risks In Sports Success In Psychological And Social Terms*

Introduction

Risk Factors In Sports, Internal Factors, A. General Health Status

Acute or chronic health issues that may develop in an athlete prior to training or competition would adversely impact performance. It also introduces a risk factor for injury. Chronic issues such as fever, respiratory tract illnesses, and diarrhea impede the athlete's performance and increase the chance of injury.

B. PSYCHOMOTOR DEVELOPMENT

Psychomotor development is a continuous process that starts during the prenatal phase and persists throughout an individual's lifespan, including alterations in movement-related behaviors. Development encompasses the notions of growth, maturity, preparedness, and learning. Growth signifies a gradual change in amount. Maturation is the process of biological changes enabling a person to attain a certain degree of maturity, influenced by the interplay of genetics and environmental factors, or the activation of latent capabilities inside the body to execute a job. The youngster must study, grow, and mature to use their strengths and enhance their capabilities. Learning is enduring behavioral modifications resulting from an individual's engagement with their environment. The notion of readiness encompasses both maturity and the requisite pre-sufficiency for a role, highlighting the significance of knowledge acquired via diverse intellectual, social, and emotional developmental experiences. The trajectory of psychomotor development must be considered in the design and execution of training programs. Specifically, acquiring the skills to be taught is contingent upon understanding the maturity

level of the children, which may result in gifted youngsters disengaging from sports or sustaining injuries.

C.PHYSICAL FITNESS

Insufficient conditioning aspects and inadequate pre-season training significantly increase the risk of injury. Tekin's research established that the incidence of injuries was elevated among football players who engaged in insufficient fitness exercise.

1.Aerobic Endurance

The energy production system that aligns with the athlete's specific sport strongly influences their performance. It is established that in physical activities lasting over one minute, the predominant energy generation mechanism that becomes effective with increased duration is aerobic energy. In sports that rely on the aerobic energy production system, inadequate aerobic endurance during training and competitions will result in diminished athletic performance and heightened injury risk.

2.Force

Athletes use force in accordance with the demands of their respective sports. This force demand may manifest as brute/unit force, fast force, or continuous force. In this regard, insufficient force exerted will result in different strains and ruptures in the muscles responsible for generating that force, hence increasing the risk of injury and diminishing performance efficacy.

3.Speed

Speed is among the most intricate topics in the realm of sports science. The physical framework necessary for speed has not been well delineated to yet. In several sporting disciplines, speed is

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an essential and critical attribute. The inadequate preparation of the components influencing speed hinders it from reaching the necessary level. Lacking sufficient speed to showcase this characteristic in the sports sector poses a danger. This risk results in diminished performance and stresses that may lead to damage.

4.Sports skills

Skill facilitates optimal synchronization across various muscular groups, enhancing the precision of movement. The crucial aspect here is the synchronization among the muscular groups executing the exercise. Consequently, executing a muscle exercise with ease is a manifestation of expertise. The proficiency of an athlete in executing fundamental technical skills in their sport mitigates the hazards associated with improper execution of these movements. The contrary of this presents a danger for both the athlete and his adversary.

5.Coordination

Coordination is the synchronization shown between the muscles involved in a movement and the central nervous system throughout that action. Therefore, it is the harmony shown during a sporting activity. The synchronization of all bodily organs involved in executing rapid, fluid, and harmonic motions during athletic exercise significantly influences performance outcomes. Currently, coordination disorders or deficiencies may lead to diminished performance and movements that diverge from their intended goal, hence increasing the risk of damage.

Aim, Methodology and Findings

D.PHYSICAL STRUCTURE

The physical attributes of an individual may sometimes provide either an advantage or a disadvantage in a particular sport, depending upon the specific physical demands of that activity. Let us attempt to disclose them.

1.Height

Height may serve as either an advantage or a disadvantage for athletes, dependent upon the specific sport in which they participate. Reduced stature gives an advantage in sports such as weightlifting and equestrianism. Height confers a competitive edge in sports like basketball, volleyball, and high jump. Nonetheless, stature is irrelevant in sports like fencing, skiing, and long-distance running. If the athlete lacks the requisite body and stature for their sport, then their height is a danger factor.

2.Weight

The domain of sport often necessitates a certain physical constitution. A significant criterion for possessing this physical structure is body weight. Excessive body weight is a disadvantage in some sports, while in others, it confers an advantage. Excessive body weight is a disadvantage in endurance sports, since it decreases oxygen consumption per kilogram. Moreover, in contexts where leaping is crucial, extra body weight constitutes a disadvantage, akin to carrying a burden on one's back. When selecting an athlete, it is essential to analyze the established physical standards for the activity, investigate familial traits, and guide the athlete towards a discipline that aligns with their physical attributes to mitigate potential dangers.

3.Joint Stability

A significant element contributing to sports injuries is the instability of the joints. This is mostly attributable to the insufficient strength of the muscles around the joints. Consequently, unstable joints elevate the likelihood of damage to the surrounding tendons or ligaments. Enhancing the strength of the muscles around the unstable joint compensates for instability, hence increasing the risk of tendon and ligament injuries. Enhancing the strength of the muscles around the unstable joint compensates for instability, hence decreasing the likelihood of tendon

and ligament injuries. In conclusion, insufficient stability in the joints diminishes joint function and elevates the chance of damage.

4. Body Fat Percentage

As is known, the body fat ratio in athletes varies according to the sport they do. The fat ratio might provide both advantages and disadvantages, depending upon the specific sport practiced. In team sports, if an athlete's body fat percentage exceeds the optimal level for that discipline, they may perceive themselves as carrying more weight, resulting in increased energy expenditure during training or competition. This results in weariness. Moreover, an elevated body fat ratio heightens the risk of injury for athletes in certain circumstances. The stress on the knees and ankles during a leap increases with an elevated body fat percentage. A deficiency in muscle and ligament strength may lead to numerous ailments. In marathon swimming, a higher body fat percentage provides an advantage in thermoregulation.

5. Age

The athlete's age might provide both advantageous and detrimental risks, depending upon the specific activity practiced. The elongation regions of a person's bones throughout the growth and developmental phase remain incompletely ossified, allowing for further expansion. Weightlifting and unregulated weight training at this ages adversely affect growth plates, inhibiting growth and development. This risk also applies to direct impacts on the growing regions. Contact sports like judo and karate, together with high-impact sports such as football, provide hazards that might hinder the development of athletes throughout their growth phase. In disciplines like gymnastics, youth confers a competitive edge. During phases before to the commencement of growth, the body's flexibility, as well as the elasticity of the muscles and spine, is significantly elevated. These attributes also provide an advantage in disciplines such as gymnastics and rhythmic gymnastics.

6. Gender

Men and women exhibit disparities in physiological response to exercise and performance levels attained. The body fat percentage is lower in males than in females. The oxygen utilization capacity is diminished in women compared to males. Women possess thinner joint and ligament tissues. This slenderness results in greater flexibility in women compared to males. Women perspire less than males and have less water loss. Women typically do not exert their physiological limitations to the same extent as males. Research indicates that the incidence of sports injuries is lower in women compared to males. Consequently, gender is seen to benefit women regarding injury risk. Consequently, women engage in less risks than males in the realm of sports.

7. Previous Injuries

A significant risk of injury for an athlete is a prior injury. The previously wounded region has a minimal risk of re-injury, irrespective of the healing condition. Furthermore, muscular atrophy in a previously damaged or surgically treated region, along with the absence of a proper rehabilitation program, heightens the risk of re-injury.

8. Muscle Tension and Muscle Tightness

Muscles must possess a certain degree of flexibility during physical exercise. If it lacks suppleness and is rigid, it presents a danger. Injuries that differ by sport arise when certain muscles are rigid. For instance, in the stiffness of the hamstring group, tendinitis and patellofemoral issues arise; inflammation of the tendons that attach muscles to bones; and in the stiffness of the iliotibial band, iliotibial band creep syndrome may occur. The rigidity of these muscles heightens the risk of injury and diminishes performance, since elasticity—an essential factor influencing joint movement angles—is compromised.

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9. Hip/Leg/Knee/Foot Weakness

Studies have shown that the most sports injuries are seen in the lower extremities. Issues arise when the leg is consistently overexerted in a certain position of the hip joint. These issues may lead to structural abnormalities in the attachments of muscles, tendons, and bones. Aspect Running on inclined surfaces necessitates foot pronation, while ascending exerts excessive strain on the Achilles tendon, and descending imposes undue stress on the heel. Irregularities in the hip, knee, and foot joints result in excessive tension on the lower extremities and specific areas being overloaded. Due to these and analogous issues, the athlete's lower extremities must possess enough strength. The contrary fosters a climate conducive to injury.

10. Lower Extremity Inequality

A discrepancy above 20 mm in leg lengths results in a notable biomechanical dysfunction. This discrepancy presents a danger to the whole lower limb. The functionality of the hip rotator and adductor muscles is compromised. This results in diminished performance and an increased risk of injury.

11. Overuse

Overuse is a significant factor contributing to sports injuries. Overuse injuries result in a rising incidence of injury. The incident starts with an indistinct ache, then escalating to heightened agony and functional impairment. This circumstance diminishes performance and heightens the danger of damage.

12. Use Less

A contributing reason to sports injuries and diminished performance is underutilization. The inadequate use of certain body parts, such as the left hand or left foot, in certain sports leads players and trainers to neglect proper preparation of these areas. For instance, in football, the

upper body, chest, head, and left foot are used by a right-footed player. The left hand is the weaker side for a right-handed basketball, volleyball, or handball player. The use of this underutilized region during competition or training diminishes athletic performance and increases the risk of injury due to inadequate preparation.

13. Physical Defect

Certain anomalies in the athlete's physical constitution expose him to several threats. Postural disorders and deficiencies in his muscular and skeletal structure may impair his performance and elevate the risk of damage.

Literature Review

E. PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS

Currently, psychological elements are widely recognized as significant determinants of an individual's health and productivity. Training and competitions that neglect the intrinsic connection between mental and physical processes and performance capability are significant factors that restrict athletic performance and contribute to injuries. The elements influencing performance mostly arise from the athlete's personality and drive. Consequently, throughout the candidate athlete selection and subsequent training, efforts are made to identify and mitigate the elements influencing their performance. Psychological factors contribute to the occurrence of sports injuries. Identifying and rectifying this issue helps mitigate one of the causes of sports injuries. Furthermore, it is well-established that athletes' performance is adversely impacted by conditions such as anxiety, depression, and neuroticism. The uncontrolled, violent, and hazardous actions shown by the athlete must be attributed to internal circumstances (psychophysics). Psychological disorders connected to personality that elevate the likelihood of sports injuries and adversely impact athletic performance may be categorized into three primary domains: emotional factors, cognitive factors, and sensomotor factors.

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1. Personality

Coaching athletes with diverse personality qualities and attaining competitive success presents a significant challenge. Personality is defined as the aggregate of physical, mental, and spiritual traits that differentiate an individual from others. The idea of personality encompasses the emotional, cognitive, attitudinal, and behavioral traits that distinguish an individual from others in both objective and subjective dimensions. Personality is intricate and multifarious. Personality encompasses several traits, including will, intellect, emotion, enthusiasm, temperament, biological structure, heredity, environmental influences, and socioeconomic variables. An individual's personality is shaped not just by their attributes but also by the impressions these traits create within their surroundings. The clearest proof of this phenomenon is that the same person is viewed, assessed, and evaluated variably, even contradictorily, across different civilizations, within distinct segments of the same society, and among various people within the same segment. The personality qualities of athletes influence their motivations for engaging in sports, their expectations, their patience and effort during training, and their responses to challenging situations in contests. By understanding the personality qualities of athletes and their correlation with performance, the coach may mitigate the possibility of personality adversely affecting performance.

2. Motivation

To attain superior athletic performance, an athlete's capacity to persist through prolonged and arduous training sessions, as well as to exhibit their accomplishments amid challenging competitive circumstances (such as opponents, spectators, and weather conditions), is intrinsically linked to their motivation. Drives or motivations are the conscious or unconscious elements that begin, disclose, maintain, and guide attitudes and actions in the construction and molding of personality. The phenomenon influenced by desires is referred to as motivation. Motivation encompasses physiological mechanisms, social behavioral variables, psychological requirements, and the reasons and consequences associated with arousal. Motivation is connected to all actions via learning

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experiences. Motivations may be categorized as either good or negative. Numerous good and bad incentives are interwoven in athletic tournaments. Anxiety may adversely impact motivation, leading the athlete to overexert oneself and perhaps sustain injuries. To effectively use motivation to enhance performance, the coach must possess a thorough understanding of his players and have precise knowledge of their interests and requirements.

3. Self

An individual's self-concept comprises his self-perceptions and the perceived judgments of others toward him. For good self-awareness to grow, he must experience unconditional love from infancy. The self-concept encompasses the aggregate of an individual's perceptions of their own personality, as well as their methods of self-assessment and evaluation. The individual's self-awareness encompasses his identity, personal attributes, responsibilities, aspirations, beliefs, and the values he deliberately adopts. The self-concept is crucial in human behavior, and a good self-concept is essential for an individual's adaptive functions and overall happiness.

Childhood connections, communication, and interactions with others facilitate an individual's socialization and self-recognition throughout life. The individual's identity materializes via responses to inquiries on their essence, capabilities, and purpose. The individual's capacity for self-perception and accurate self-evaluation hinders their achievement and happiness. A skilled athlete could attempt activities above their capability, believing in their aptitude, while an unskilled athlete may also pursue unattainable objectives under the same misconception. Coaches must use caution in their critiques, particularly after the failures of young athletes, to prevent harm to their self-esteem and the erosion of their self-confidence.

4. Perception

Perception is the awareness of our internal and external environments. The impulses received via our sensory organs are experienced to a certain degree. Two distinct individuals in the same

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environment may observe disparate phenomena. Perceptions are influenced by an individual's experiences, education, focus of attention, and emotions. Perception is the individual's attainment of awareness about the impressions received from the environment via the five senses and from the body via the internal senses. Through perceptual acuity, the athlete comprehends the significance of their efforts, the status of their adversaries, and the strategies they need to implement. An athlete must first recognize their own physique. Body perception encompasses the form, size, location, and structure of the limbs, as well as the range of motion of the joints and the spatial directions of movement. Moreover, spatial perception, temporal perception, and movement perception influence athletic performance.

5. Concentration

Concentration refers to the directed concentration of attention on a certain point. In mastering athletic actions and their accurate execution in a competitive setting, concentration must be directed towards a single focal point. If players focus their concentrate on matters unrelated to the game, they cannot effectively execute their responsibilities in accordance with the game's progression. Players divert their limited concentrate to other concerns, resulting in inefficient energy allocation that hampers their effectiveness in the game. Athletes in a situation of significant loss may struggle to execute their talents well as they become preoccupied with the abilities of their opponents, leading to a decline in performance. Provided that circumstances are favorable, the athlete should be given the chance to replenish expended energy via brief intermissions. If breaks and loads occur in a consistent sequence, the expended energy may be recuperated. The cause of concentration difficulties should be identified first. A multitude of factors, including lack of desire, emotional and psychological problems, sickness, boring or excessive training, fear, and autonomic nervous system abnormalities, might impede the ability to concentrate on a single spot.

6. Competition and Ambition

The athlete competes against his/her opponent to achieve success in the tournaments. The athlete battles against both himself and their surroundings in every competition. Although competition often enhances an organism's motivation to perform at peak capability, it also elicits previously unrecognized competitive emotions in athletes. The athlete engages in the competition using not just physical abilities but also psychological states, including emotions and ideas. Competition is recognized as a potent motivational instrument, facilitating optimal talent display for numerous participants; however, athletes experiencing both low and high anxiety within the same competitive context approach the competition with a win-at-all-costs mentality. In this instance, they behave with ambition. The sensation of ambition, which prompts the athlete to engage in self-destructive or environmentally detrimental behavior, is undesirable. Nonetheless, coaches often misapply the word ambitious, opting for aggressive and resolute instead. Athletes taught to play aggressively exhibit heightened risk-taking, disorganized actions, more collisions, and more frequent fouls. Injuries may arise, potentially impairing performance.

In instances when an athlete's likelihood of success is inherently diminished, due to factors such as inadequate fitness, inappropriate body size for the activity, or insufficient training, participation in competition should be avoided. The competitive impulse needs deliberate affection and oversight. Otherwise, achieving the appropriate performance becomes challenging due to perceptual problems, erroneous actions, and inadequate synchronization.

7. Don't Take Risks

Certain athletes often engage in risk-taking actions. Such antics often engage the crowd and get extensive media attention. An activity is deemed dangerous when there is a specific objective, however uncertainty exists over the adequacy of the available resources and capabilities to attain that objective. Certain athletes may have a propensity for risk-taking as a personality characteristic. Nonetheless, other more factors contribute to risk-taking in the sports context. Athletes may do very perilous tasks that exceed their existing capabilities due to their desire to avoid failure and maintain visibility. Additional factors for athletes to take risks include the

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aspiration to please the coach, to seem favorable to the audience, to imitate athletes that partake in hazardous activities, high motivation, animosity towards opponents, or an inability to accept failure. Hazardous acts seldom have favorable outcomes. They often detrimentally impact performance and may result in injury. Coaches must refrain from making remarks and exhibiting behaviors that promote hazardous acts to ensure players maintain a prolonged and healthy sports career.

8. Aggression

Currently, aggressiveness is becoming more prominent in sports discussions. In everyday life, violent actions arise from numerous challenges for several causes; but, in sports, such aggression is permissible according to the rules, since success relies on overcoming the opponent's hurdles. When the rules are transgressed, either the opponent or the individual will suffer consequences and face punishment. Certain athletes have a propensity for aggressive tendencies. The assignment of jobs involving opponent contact, particularly for defensive players, heightens the danger of injury or disciplinary action. Displaced hostility is seen in some sportsmen. In this instance, the athlete may channel his/her anger not towards the primary cause but onto other people or items. An athlete dissatisfied with their coach may vent frustration at teammates by blaming a poor pass, whereas an athlete upset with the referee may exhibit self-directed hostility. Guilt, disappointment, and regret are the catalysts for self-directed anger. A conversation must be established that prevents young athletes from experiencing emotions.

9. Anxiety

Anxiety has both beneficial and detrimental influences on human behavior. It manifests effects that are both favorably motivating and conducive to greater achievement, while also imposing restrictions on mobility, resulting in diminished success and indecision. Elevated state anxiety impairs performance. Conversely, an individual with diminished state anxiety has a deficiency in drive for achievement. Research indicates that contests induce anxiety in athletes. The impact of this scenario on the outcome is contingent upon several elements, including personality traits,

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age, gender, living circumstances, experience, and environmental conditions. Athletes with elevated trait anxiety levels are recognized to have more state anxiety than their counterparts, which may impede performance.

10.Fear

Freud characterizes fear as a person's response to a perceived danger. Fear may originate from several sources. The majority of worries encountered in sports stem from the sporting environment and arise from the process of learning. All athletes must prioritize their health and prevent injuries. In some athletes, this circumstance may become extreme, instilling dread and adversely impacting performance. In some athletes, the prospect of harming their opponent may also induce terror. Athletes may sense dread stemming from their own actions as much as the violence of their opponents. In those with stable personalities capable of psychologically managing low to moderate amounts of fear, terror may sometimes enhance performance. This scenario is typically seen in fitness-related issues. Conversely, anxiety diminishes performance in tasks requiring coordination and strategy, such as gymnastics and competitive games. The first step to mitigate fear is to acknowledge its presence, essentially to admit the dread. Disseminating knowledge on the factors that induce fear serves as an additional method to mitigate dread. The athlete who comprehensively understands himself, his opponent, his responsibilities in the game, the audience, and the referee, while articulating his objectives clearly and suitably, will mitigate the anxiety that hinders his performance.

11.Stress

Stress is a condition arising from the physical and mental pressure on an organism, manifesting as both psychological and physical illnesses. The organism's psychological responses to stress are influenced by personality characteristics and environmental circumstances. The athlete is perpetually in situations that might induce stress from both training and contests. In significant events when players' physical abilities, technical skills, and tactical acumen are closely

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matched, victory is determined by the team that effectively controls stress. To mitigate stress as a hindrance to athlete performance, coaches must first thoroughly understand their athletes and identify the causes and degrees of their stress. The sources of pressure experienced by the athlete should be addressed and, if required, psychorelaxation techniques (such as progressive relaxation, biofeedback, autogenic training, transcendental meditation, and hypnosis) should be used.

12. Psychological Loads

All high-performance sporting activities include both psychological and physical burdens. Athletes has varying capacity for psychological burden. Identical circumstances may yield varying outcomes across athletes, depending upon their personality characteristics and experiences. A breakdown in the psycho-physical equilibrium of athletes due to heightened psychological load results in diminished performance. Monotony arises when same warm-up and training routines are performed again or when the instructor consistently use the same terminology for admonition. This monotony will lead to the athlete being uninspired, lethargic, fatigued, and experiencing a decrease in blood pressure, which will result in performance variations and attention difficulties. Psychological saturation may lead to athlete demotivation or anxiety, impairing their mental faculties and resulting in diminished performance.

13. Emotional and Mental Conflicts

A competitive athlete may regularly encounter emotional and psychological issues in both their everyday life and during training and contests. An athlete desiring to picnic with peers on a pleasant day may encounter emotional tension due to the simultaneous want to prepare in anticipation of the forthcoming championship contest. A basketball player may have a mental conflict during a game between shooting the ball into the hoop or passing it to a teammate. Conflict arises when two or more conflicting impulses simultaneously influence a person; these motivations manifest differently based on their nature, intensity, and contextual surroundings. An individual experiencing difficulties in decision-making over a certain subject and exhibiting

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tension is likely in a state of conflict. Psychological insights play a crucial role in conflict resolution. The coach should consider the athlete's age, cognitive ability, and emotional condition while acting on this information. Athletes with self-confidence issues may be assigned new, tangible, and simpler duties. A coach familiar with his athlete may foresee potential challenges and implement measures to prevent confrontation. When athletes' aspirations and objectives collide with expectations and contextual circumstances, violent responses may arise due to emotional and psychological turmoil. This increases the likelihood of harm.

14. Belief System

Athletes possess self-beliefs. This belief system encompasses notions such as "I have never attempted this before; I am incapable of executing this maneuver." Failure to eradicate these ideas will result in adverse outcomes on the field.

15. Obsessions

Athletes possess certain obsessions rooted on their prior experiences. An earlier injury may preclude them from engaging in that posture upon its establishment.

16. Tendency to Find Victims

Individuals who thrive on the sentiment of pity evade accountability for their failures. They seek to identify an external party to attribute responsibility, so generating a justification. They possess a personality that almost safeguards their vulnerabilities.

Argument

F. SUDDEN DEATHS IN SPORTS

Sudden death is an infrequent but unwanted occurrence in sports. The World Health Organization addresses incidents characterized by symptom onset between 30 seconds to a maximum of 6 hours post-exercise, with mortality occurring within 24 hours. These occurrences arise from healthy, traumatic, or atraumatic origins. Exercise-induced sudden fatalities may occur across many age demographics. Observations indicate that occurrences at an early age are often attributed to congenital defects, while those at a later age are linked to ischemic heart disease and its sequelae. The first scientific investigation of sudden fatalities in sports was carried out by Schmid and Hornof from Czechoslovakia. The researchers documented 76 instances of unexpected death among athletes from 1925 to 1960. Subsequently, Izeki from Japan investigated and studied 507 incidents of sudden death among high school athletes from 1962 to 1969. It was concluded that the majority of these fatalities resulted from drowning and sudden cardiac failure. The primary causes of sudden mortality in sports are cardiac-related incidents. Moreover, heat stroke, hypothermia-induced heat loss, dehydration, or fluid depletion are other causes of rapid death.

EXTERNAL FACTORS

A. FIELD RELATED FACTORS

Factors pertaining to the field may be analyzed under three primary categories: the physical conditions of the field, the features of the terrain, and the lighting conditions.

1. Risks created by the physical conditions of the field

The venue for the tournament or training may sometimes provide dangers due to its physical circumstances. These hazards should be mitigated whenever possible, and if elimination is not

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feasible, they should be acknowledged. The physical conditions of the field provide the following hazards.

a. Whether the field is open or closed

Both open and closed playgrounds have inherent dangers. In outdoor sports, players are mostly impacted by the detrimental impacts of meteorological conditions. Factors include severe temperatures, both high and low, as well as precipitation.

For athletes training or competing in enclosed environments, the primary consideration is to adequately heat or cool the space. Insufficient heating of the hall may lead to several health issues, increased risk of accident, and diminished performance. Moreover, sportsmen like entrances to mitigate their elevated body temperature while exercising. Locations with air circulation, such as entrances, provide dangers such as colds and stiffness in different regions for perspiring athletes. We believe that these seemingly easy concerns need the coach's consideration to mitigate dangers.

b. Lack of safety distance:

Athletes sometimes cannot decelerate their acquired momentum on the playing field and are compelled to leave the field. This is where the physical conditions of the arena and the venue are significant. On the absence of adequate braking or deceleration zones, the athlete is compelled to collide with wire fences on open fields and walls in indoor arenas. Such situations are often seen in amateur tournaments, lower league events, and indoor sports meets. The absence of adequate braking or deceleration distance is a danger that diminishes performance and heightens the likelihood of damage. Furthermore, the maintenance of cleanliness and the consistent provision of enough braking/deceleration distance are critical concerns. In sports venues, just the playing surface is sanitized while other sections are neglected.

c. Failure to take other security measures on site

In the realm of sports, hazardous zones beyond the playing field must be identified beforehand, and these locations should be secured to mitigate or eradicate the risk to players.

2. Risks posed by the ground

A research in the USA identified that one of the four primary causes of injuries sustained by professional team players throughout the competition season was the playing surface. Consequently, the ground is a danger factor in its own right. The issues we face on the ground are as follows:

a. The ground has lost its evenness

The primary concern is the evenness of the terrain. Athletes on uneven terrain are akin to navigating a field of hazards. Numerous outdoor fields deteriorate into hazardous areas, losing their smoothness owing to vigorous sports activities, adverse weather conditions, and insufficient upkeep. In indoor sports, the integrity of the flooring may deteriorate owing to structural failures resulting from inadequate maintenance or swelling induced by water absorption. Moreover, several sports are conducted on mats. The mat's loss of smoothness presents a similar issue. Consequently, performance on a surface that has deteriorated diminishes, and the likelihood of damage increases.

b. The ground has lost its stability.

Particularly in sports halls, inadequate maintenance or vigorous athletic activities may lead to the deterioration and displacement of the flooring materials. Additionally, in sports conducted on mats, there may be collapses or bulges resulting from the internal material of the mat. This entails dynamic (interactive) zones. Consequently, the stability of the floor is compromised. Moreover, in activities such as skiing or ice skating, the melting of some sections of the surface

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undermines the stability of the track. The floor's instability, resulting from the aforementioned factors, diminishes athletic performance and heightens the danger of injury.

c. The ground is wet

The primary concern in wide fields is the risk of moist ground conditions. Identical hazards exist in sports conducted on mats inside enclosed spaces, where the surface may get wet for numerous causes. Some of these hazards include liquids consumed during stops, athletes expectorating on the ground, and perspiration from athletes contaminating the surface. These issues should be resolved by promptly mopping and cleaning the moisture. Failure to rectify the issues will compromise the athlete's equilibrium, resulting in falls and slips, which will adversely impact their performance and increase the likelihood of injury.

d. The ground is frozen

This issue is seen in open areas. Due to worsening weather conditions, several portions of the field are freezing. This inherently poses a danger. The athlete is unable to perform optimally on icy terrain. Performance diminishes, and the likelihood of damage increases.

e. The ground is dirty

In venues designated for team sports, the cleaning of the playing surface often occurs just inside the designated playing area. This neglected concern is that leaving the designated playing area results in the formation of a slippery surface composed of dust and grime. The regions around the playing area in the hall, often traversed in non-sport footwear, are the most unsanitary and hazardous. Currently, the use of places outside the playing field by some players engaged in specialized training must be acknowledged. If these parameters are disregarded, the athlete will experience diminished performance and an elevated risk of injury.

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f. Presence of foreign matter on the ground

The hazards posed by foreign items on the ground or those projected into the field during the tournament must not be overlooked. This will result in the athlete slipping and losing their equilibrium, akin to traps positioned under their feet. These factors will undoubtedly impair the athlete's performance and elevate the risk of injury.

3. Risks caused by lighting conditions

In both outdoor night contests and inside events, insufficient illumination of the venue presents a hazard. In our nation, the lighting cannot be deemed adequate, particularly in state buildings leased for training sessions. Many tournaments are conducted under insufficient illumination conditions. Insufficient illumination will adversely impact the athlete's performance and hinder their ability to perceive potential injury risks in their environment. Moreover, sunlight might provide a danger factor in daytime events or training sessions, potentially impairing competitors' visibility and sightlines.

B. FACTORS RELATED TO TOOLS AND EQUIPMENT

1. Clothing

The athlete's clothing is of significant significance. The appropriateness of clothes on the body influences his performance. Factors to consider include the weight of the clothes, the rate of perspiration absorption, the fabric type, the cut style, the comfort of stitching points against the body, and the overall fit of the garment. Furthermore, if the attire is intended for outdoor use, its hue must be suitable for the season and prevailing weather conditions. Inappropriate clothes for the athlete may restrict mobility, and the material composition will adversely impact performance and increase the risk of injury. Currently, global sportswear firms are engaged in intense rivalry. Daily, a new product is introduced to the global market and is empirically evaluated by the athletes that use it.

2. Shoes

Footwear is the main equipment for an athlete. All equilibrium, movement, and stability rely on them. Unsuitable footwear may adversely affect an athlete's performance during training and competition, while also increasing the chance of injury. The characteristics of a sports shoe differ based on the specific sport. The characteristics of running shoes, indoor shoes, and football shoes are consistently distinct.

There are four basic points to consider when determining the athlete's shoe type:

1. Compatibility between shoes and sports ground.
2. The construction method and components (sections) of the shoe
3. Size of the shoe and its suitability to the foot
4. Fit between shoe and foot

In general, the features to look for in a sports shoe are as follows:

1. The sole should be thick enough and supported by a soft sole that will absorb shock when running on hard surfaces.
2. The heel should be slightly high to prevent excessive load on the muscles at the back of the calf and the Achilles tendon that connects to the heel.
3. The back of the shoe should be raised to grip the heel well.
4. There should be an orthopedic cushion in the sole of the shoe that fills and supports the inner arch.
5. When wearing thick cotton socks inside, they should be one size larger if necessary, so that they do not squeeze the foot and leave the toe free.

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3. Shoelace

A shoelace that becomes undone during training or competition presents a hazard for the athlete, their teammates, and their opponents. It presents a hazard if the shoelace is trodden upon, if the athlete inadvertently steps on the untied shoelace with the opposite foot, or if it becomes ensnared in the footwear of an opponent or teammate.

4. Ball

In team sports, the ball used in the game also presents a danger issue. Inflating the ball beyond or below the standard pressure poses a danger. Primarily, in hand-based sports like basketball, volleyball, and handball, the fingers and wrist are susceptible to injury; in football, the ankle, head, and neck are at danger. These factors may result in diminished performance and an increased likelihood of injury.

5. File

Certain sports use nets. Nets are present in the goals of football and handball, in the basket of basketball, between the posts of volleyball, and in tennis. This net/net is seldom seen in many sporting activities; yet, it may sometimes lead to incidents when hands, fingers, or feet get entangled, resulting in sprains, strains, or injuries. In this regard, while the net/net is hardly seen, it is a potential danger of damage.

6. Goalposts/poles

It is well-established that some sports have goals. (For example, football and handball.) Additionally, there are corner posts in football, for instance. In several sports, nets delineate the fields. The nets are further affixed to the poles. (For example, volleyball and tennis.) These posts are constructed from materials that may be struck during the game, posing a risk of harm, but their prevalence varies by sport.

7. Stability of tools

In both equipment-based sports and some activities using equipment, the instability of the apparatus poses inherent dangers. The instability of equipment, including asymmetrical parallels, parallel bars, and balancing bars used in gymnastics, undermines the athlete's equilibrium, induces involuntary movements, detrimentally impacts performance, and heightens the risk of injury. Moreover, the instability of the apparatuses that secure weights on free weights used in resistance training, as well as the equipment employed in diverse weight training regimens, presents a potential hazard. Trainers and players should consider these concerns.

8. Protective materials

Athletes use specific protective gear based on the sport. Utilizing equipment sized appropriately for the athlete mitigates the chance of damage. Depending on the sport, protective equipment may include knee pads, elbow pads, mouthguards, eye protection, gaiters, wrist guards, thigh pads, calf pads, and helmets. The use of inadequate protective equipment or the absence of needed protective gear in certain circumstances always poses a risk that diminishes performance and increases the likelihood of injury.

9. Taping (Bandage)

Bandages used by athletes in compliance with regulations include inherent defensive qualities. Historically, bandages were only used for the treatment of injuries sustained by athletics. Currently, to mitigate the risk of damage, many sportsmen choose for the application of bandages, regardless of prior injuries in that region. Bandages has defensive and therapeutic properties. The essential concern is that the bandage is placed appropriately, ensuring it does not impede the functionality of unaffected regions or those not susceptible to harm. Otherwise,

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it unequivocally results in diminished performance because to the heightened risk of injury and reduced mobility.

C. FACTORS RELATED TO THE GAME (COMPETITION)

1. Type of athlete

The main consideration is the issues that may emerge based on whether the sport is classified as contact or non-contact. The likelihood of injury in contact sports (such as basketball, football, handball, wrestling, and boxing) exceeds that in non-contact sports (including tennis, table tennis, swimming, athletics, and gymnastics). Consequently, the first danger pertains to the nature of the activity.

2. The status of the team or athlete

The team's league rating or the athlete's competition ranking serves as a risk factor, contingent upon its significance. The tension among players of a club that has reached the relegation place in their most recent match, together with their conduct during the game, presents a significant danger to the agenda. In this psychological milieu, athletes' rule infractions elevate the danger of damage to both themselves and their opponents. Moreover, that stressful setting may hinder their ability to demonstrate optimal performance.

3. The athlete's status within the team

The athlete's conduct varies based on his position within the team, the duration of his playtime, and the extent to which he meets expectations. For instance, an athlete who perceives insufficient playing time may, upon entering the game, execute an inappropriate maneuver, make an unwarranted pass, utilize a ball incorrectly, or engage in an unnecessary confrontation.

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This detrimental conduct results in a decline in the team's overall performance or the athlete fostering an atmosphere that is detrimental to himself.

4. Substitute player

In team sports, replacement players can fail to warm up enough due to uncertainty around their entry into the game. Their bodies may cool depending on the game's length. The incorporation of replacement players in the game exposes them to danger. Both demonstrate subpar performance and their physiques are susceptible to damage. Consequently, replacement players need to adequately warm up and strive to maintain their body temperature while seated on the sidelines.

5. Level of the competition

The athlete's degree of sport participation (amateur, professional, or local, national) inherently influences the caliber of competition or training they will engage in. The performance shown in a local competition and a nationwide competition varies significantly in caliber. As competition intensifies, the hazards faced by the athlete during the competition or in the preparatory training phase also increase. The preparations for both amateur and professional competitions introduce additional hazards for participants and their opponents.

6. Change of target

Athletes often prepare for a certain objective during a designated season. An unforeseen change or reduction in this objective adversely impacts participants in tournaments, particularly in team-based games. A team concentrated on the title, rather than psychologically preparing for the third or fourth place match after their elimination from the finals, adversely impacts their performance in that contest. In such contests, acts driven by rage heighten the danger of damage for sportsmen. The primary obligation rests with management and trainees. Athletes must be

apprised that objectives may shift, and they should be assisted in concentrating on a revised goal promptly.

7. Game rules and regulations

One scenario in which the athlete is vulnerable is the regulations of the sport. Inadequate application of the game rules will result in heightened difficulty and an increase in erratic movements.

This entails an increased risk of harm. It unequivocally detrimentally impacts performance. Literature indicates that 25 percent of sports injuries result from rule-violating conduct.

8. Displacement factor

Away matches are a risk factor for athletes. This event occurs primarily due to road fatigue, competing in a different and unfamiliar field, an unfamiliar bed, unfamiliar food, the influence of the opposing team's fans, and the effects of away matches.

A study has determined that athletes experience the following problems during away games:

1. Fatigue
2. Weakness
3. Ear, tooth and stomach ache
4. Diarrhea
5. Cold, runny nose, flu infection
6. Waist and muscle pain

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9. Experience factor

Inexperience is a danger element for adolescent athletes. In particular, the vigor of youth leads novice athletes to inadvertently jeopardize their safety during training or competition. This danger may sometimes result in injury to them or their companions. Furthermore, unskilled conduct may result in excessive energy use and suboptimal performance. In addition to the drawbacks associated with inexperience, it is essential to evaluate if the experience yields good or bad outcomes. Athletes that have favorable experiences have a substantial edge. The responsibilities assigned to the athlete from their initiation into sports must align with their capabilities and serve as a foundation for their success. Conversely, despite the athlete's extensive preparation and competitive experience, they are mostly unproductive events and do not provide a competitive edge. Particularly poor situations encountered early in their athletic careers lead many brilliant youngsters to disengage from sports.

10. Expectations factor

Sports include certain expectations for participation. The athlete's ability to meet these expectations or the total loss of hope in achieving them may hinder his optimal performance. The current danger on the agenda is the expectation factor. Given the substantial cash advantages and prestige associated with competition, athletes may feel compelled to pursue victory at any cost, so elevating the danger to themselves and their opponents.

D. SOCIAL FACTORS

As the significance and incentives of sports in society expand, and the social standing of athletes elevates, the nature and structure of social connections likewise evolve. Beyond the family and educational connections of the player, social ties emerge from their athletic role, including interactions with the coach, club administration, referees, fans, and the media. Each of these factors influences the athlete's performance, either favorably or adversely, depending on its location.

1. Parent factor

While the families of athletes serve as their primary supports, they may sometimes provide dangers that may contribute to accidents and diminish performance for numerous reasons. The athlete's marital status influences the involvement of their parents, siblings, spouse, and children in family life. Unreasonably elevated expectations of youngsters can result in disappointment in sports. Despite operating at their full potential, they are unable to achieve the intended objective. A family without sports expertise may anticipate their athletic child's inability to succeed and hence offers futile encouragement. Conversely, a youngster from an athletic household may exhibit behavior indicative of a need to validate their abilities. Children's behavioral development is influenced by familial and environmental influences. Consequently, it is essential for families to assist their children in identifying acceptable sports and to provide appropriate commentary about victory and defeat. A further issue is to the conduct of families post-competition. Families must assist young individuals in comprehending that both victory and defeat are possible outcomes, akin to other occurrences during competition, including the discussions held with their children post-competition.

2. Co-factor

Particularly accomplished sportsmen sometimes marry at a young age to attain a conventional lifestyle. The partner of a young, accomplished athlete is a significant consideration at this juncture. Some sportsmen exhibit variations in their conduct and attitude before and after marriage. Occasionally, these variances provide beneficial outcomes, but at other times, they alter the athlete's personality entirely. Occasionally, particularly under the influence of their spouse, the athlete develops an obsession with aspects such as increased team participation, enhanced performance, surpassing other players, achieving the status of the team's top player, and the financial exploitation of their talent. This leads them to behave differently towards their teammates, coaches and managers. Comparable actions may undermine the cohesion and collaboration of the team, thereby impacting overall performance, while also prompting the

athlete to exhibit aggression within the group, so fostering a detrimental environment for themselves.

3. Referee factor

For athletics, the referee is a significant variable. In team sports, competitors are particularly interested in identifying the referee for the next match. The athlete enters the contest aware of the referee's identity. This engenders a bias within them. This official is competent. This referee appropriates everything. Regrettably, this referee exhibited an undue fixation on me throughout the last match. We are in a predicament; this referee consistently favors the home side over the visiting squad. Such obsessions may induce the athlete to display aggressive conduct in competitive settings. This conduct may hinder his ability to completely exhibit his talent and result in moves that might lead to damage. The referees' inadequate application of the rules exacerbates the game's difficulty, diminishes performance, and heightens the chance of injury. Particularly accomplished sportsmen often marry at a young age to pursue a conventional lifestyle. The partner of a young, successful athlete is a significant consideration at this juncture. Some sportsmen exhibit variations in their conduct and attitude before and after marriage. Occasionally, these variances provide beneficial outcomes, but at other times, they alter the athlete's personality entirely. Occasionally, particularly under the influence of their spouse, the athlete develops an obsession with aspects such as increased team participation, enhanced performance, surpassing other players, achieving the status of the team's greatest player, and the financial gains others get from their efforts. This results in altered behavior towards their colleagues, coaches, and supervisors. Comparable actions may undermine the cohesion and collaboration of the team, thereby impacting overall performance, while also prompting the athlete to exhibit aggression within the group, so fostering a detrimental environment for themselves.

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4. Media factor

Following an athlete's early media exposure, changes in their personality ensue. They begin to perceive their significance and presence on the agenda. The healthiness or unhealthiness of an athlete's prior personality is directly linked to the alterations in their personality concerning their media presence, irrespective of their health status. Unhealthy or immature personalities, often seen in athletes who attain fame and wealth at a young age, may result in detrimental behavioral changes both within the team and towards the coaching staff and management. Moreover, depending on the favorable or unfavorable tone of media coverage, the athlete may sometimes feel compelled to validate his abilities. In such situations, the athlete may engage in acts that pose a risk of harm or undertake inconsequential actions that might diminish both individual and team performance.

5. Money factor

When athletes choose sports as a vocation, their earnings are determined by the specific sport they participate in and their levels of accomplishment. In some sports, the earnings may amount to hundreds of thousands of dollars. Diverse behavioral patterns may emerge based on the personality of athletes who begin to earn substantial sums at an early age. These behavioral modifications hinder the athlete's performance during training or competition and may result in actions that pose hazards to themselves, their peers, and their adversaries. Should foster intrinsic drive in athletes rather than extrinsic motivation. For athletes that prioritize internal success, monetary considerations, an external success component, will no longer pose a concern.

7. Education and culture factor

The athlete is not a mechanized being. He is a person. He has a framework founded on social, psychological, and physiological principles. An essential aspect in the development of this structure is the education and culture he acquires. The athlete's educational background and

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cultural exposure influence his comprehension of his profession, his expectations from it, and the anticipations of his family, surroundings, and team. This inherently optimizes or diminishes the performance he will exhibit and the risks he undertakes while delivering this performance. Another issue that may impact the athlete's performance is encountering educational and training difficulties stemming from faults in time management. The athlete's aspiration to remain competitive, coupled with rigorous training and external competitions, juxtaposes with the necessity to pursue academic endeavors, driven by the apprehension of becoming uneducated post-career, thereby jeopardizing the athlete's capacity to excel in both sports and education. The athlete must first be educated on excellent time management and possess the conviction that he can attain success via meticulous preparation. Moreover, communication issues and disparities in expectations that may emerge among a team of athletes from varied educational and cultural backgrounds provide a risk factor for the team's performance.

8. Language factor

The linguistic aspect is particularly important in situations involving foreign coaches or players. Should the translation issue with the foreign coach remain unresolved, the resultant tension over their intentions on the field would inevitably impact the team's performance and the players' execution. A similar issue arises when players are unable to effectively communicate their intentions to their coaches. In addition to these factors, the insufficient communication between foreign players and their teammates in team games is also detrimental. Moreover, this linguistic issue also affects masseurs and physicians to whom international athletes attempt to communicate their bodily issues. The athlete's inability to adequately articulate his grievance adversely impacts his performance and heightens the danger of injury.

9. Manager factor

Managers represent an additional danger element for athletes. Managerial behavior towards athletes influences them variably, contingent upon their personalities, experiences, educational backgrounds, and ages. The manager's reaction, demeanor, or statements prior to a competition or training session may lead the athlete to display a negative attitude during that event, adversely impact both individual and team performance, and prompt actions that could jeopardize the health of themselves, their peers, or their opponents. Moreover, over interference by management in technical issues concerning the technical personnel is a prevalent issue in our nation. The observation of this intervention by the athletes is likewise detrimental.

10. Audience factor

The intricate nature of the human physiology and the mechanisms of skill acquisition remain unknown, making it challenging to ascertain the influence of the audience on the athlete. It has been noted that the audience influences the stress experienced by the athlete during competition, with the level of tension varying based on the task's difficulty and complexity. The athlete's assessment of the crowd's impact during or prior to the performance is contingent upon their personality structure and subsequently influences their response to the audience. Based on this knowledge, it can be said that the audience aspect is one of the risks for the athlete. The supportive or disparaging demeanor of the crowd, whether at the athlete's or team's home venue or the unfavorable reactions shown during away games, is one of the elements influencing the athlete. Both good and negative cheering may influence an athlete's performance and the likelihood of injury. Some athletes remain unaffected by such occurrences, while others may have adverse effects from the cheers directed at them or their team, particularly while under unmanageable strain.

The audience's cheering might sometimes adversely impact the athlete. Augmenting the frequency of exhibition matches conducted before an audience and periodically hosting open training sessions for spectators may mitigate the impact of the crowd on sportsmen.

11. Term contract

The duration of athletes' contracts, whether long-term or short-term, influences their performance based on their personality traits. This may sometimes provide very beneficial or highly detrimental outcomes.

12. Staff changes

Numerous variables within the squad, including player dynamics, technical staff, administrative conditions, match scheduling, and venue, adversely impact the majority of players.

13. Uncertainty situation

Numerous variables within the squad, including player dynamics, technical staff, administrative conditions, match scheduling, and venue, adversely impact the majority of players.

E. TRAINING RELATED FACTORS

Training presents a danger of harm under four specific scenarios. The first condition is insufficient warm-up, the second involves inappropriate training, and the third pertains to exerting pressure on the athlete in a state of overtraining. The fourth most precarious concern is the execution of weight training in an unthinking and unsystematic manner. Let us now elucidate these criteria sequentially:

1. Warm-up

The athlete must do the requisite warm-up prior to training or competition. Insufficient and improper warm-up poses a significant risk of injury and results in subpar performance. We encounter three categories of athletes who engage in warm-up activities on sports grounds. The

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first group of athletes warms up independently with individualized exercises, the second group engages in a standardized warm-up program collectively, and the third group warms up under the guidance of a coach. Athletes see the notion of warming up via three distinct lenses based on their educational background, athletic experience, professionalism, and performance metrics. For certain individuals, the warm-up phase may be deemed unnecessary at the start of training or competition. For many athletes, warming up is the most crucial and essential component of training or competition. For some athletes, warming up is a required exercise before to training or competition. A survey of the literature on this issue reveals that warm-up exercises positively influence athletic performance across all performed research. Proper warm-up enhances both aerobic (oxygen-dependent) and anaerobic (oxygen-independent) energy output. Research indicates that muscle strength improves with proper warm-up in relation to neuro-muscular activity. A warmed muscle exhibits increased flexibility and enhanced contraction speed. Warming up enhances muscle suppleness, allowing greater joint amplitudes (range of motion). Joint mobility is enhanced with warming up. Furthermore, warming up enhances target direction and movement coordination. Generally, warming up enhances attributes like as endurance, speed, strength, leaping, and flexibility. Simultaneously, a significant health benefit of warming up is its capacity to reduce the risk of sports-related injuries, including those affecting muscles, ligaments, and tendons.

2. Wrong training

Inadequate training of the athlete predisposes him/her to injury. Excessive pressure on dense muscular regions poses many dangers, pushing the boundaries of tiredness and resulting in lactic acid accumulation. Moreover, if an overworked athlete's lactic acid levels have risen above acceptable thresholds, it indicates a disruption in the athlete's coordination, targeting ability, and focus. This will result in an imbalance in motions, diminish performance, and increase the risk of injury. The matter at hand pertains to the inadequacies encountered during a training session. Inaccurate periodization of training always leads to a divergence from the intended objectives. Improperly periodized training adversely impacts the intended performance.

3.Overtraining

The greatest fear for athletes is to get overtrained. Currently, overtraining is mostly a psychological manifestation of persistent weariness that often arises towards the conclusion of the training cycle. Muscular, nervous, and psychological elements are influential here.

Symptoms seen in an athlete in an overtraining state are:

1. The athlete becomes restless.
2. Gets tired easily
3. Complains of headache and back pain.
4. There is a lot of sweating.
5. Shortness of breath is observed
6. Irregular sleep occurs
7. Desire to compete decreases
8. Appetite decreases
9. Weight loss may be on the agenda
10. Tachycardia is observed in the morning, that is, the pulse rate increases.
11. In case of overtraining, the coach must cooperate with the sports physician.

4.Weight training

Neglecting some factors during weight training may increase the chance of injury for athletes. Initially, it is essential to do an adequate warm-up and stretching regimen before to engaging in

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weight training. In addition to the basic warm-up, particular regions targeted for weight training must undergo specialized warm-up exercises. When use free weights in training, the weight should be maintained in proximity to the body. The connection and compression points of free weights must be inspected prior to each lift. Breathing must be consistently practiced throughout resistance training. Athletes should unequivocally refrain from engaging in humor during weight training sessions. It is crucial that the weight training program be tailored to the specific objectives. Neglecting these aspects in weight training hinders the attainment of desired performance and increases the risk of injury.

F. ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

The individual and environmental circumstances necessary for training or competition, as well as the specific environmental components present in the training or competition setting, vary and significantly influence the athlete's performance.

1. Circadian Rhythm

The human body undergoes many physiological and psychological cycles throughout a 24-hour period. All of these rhythms are referred to as circadian rhythms. The parameters of the human body's neuromuscular coordination, physical labor capacity, response time, muscle endurance, grip strength, joint mobility, body temperature, heart rate, blood plasma volume, oxygen consumption, and protein concentration exhibit varying cycles. The human body is recognized to possess about three hundred thousand physiological activities that exhibit periods of high efficiency and vitality, as well as intervals of diminished efficiency and sluggishness during a 24-hour cycle. For instance, whereas liver glycogen storage, an emergency energy reserve, peaks in the late morning, it begins to diminish as nighttime approaches. The endocrine system has unique circadian cycles that influence muscle tone and strength for athletic adaptation. The cortisol hormone peaks each morning upon awakening and thereafter declines to its lowest level by nightfall. Melatonin, a hormone associated with weariness, has variations influenced by dietary patterns and circadian rhythms. Consequently, the body's circadian rhythm during

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training or competition hours might positively or negatively influence performance. Athletes face risks in training and competitive settings characterized by temporal discrepancies. In these conditions, performance diminishes, and the danger of damage increases during training and contests conducted at unconventional hours. Consequently, training hours should align with competition hours to facilitate the body's adaptation to the circadian rhythm at that time; failing to do so may result in diminished athletic performance and an elevated risk of injury.

2. Jet lag (Time change)

Jet lag is a syndrome that often arises from prolonged trips. There exists a physical and psychological incompatibility that arises post-flights between places with certain time discrepancies. Abrupt alterations in time disrupt internal biological cycles and induce disorientation. Long flights in the east and west directions particularly interrupt the sleep-wake cycle. Consequently, due to the physiological alterations that transpire, jet lag manifests, leading to adverse symptoms like weariness, sad moods, headaches, impaired concentration, diminished appetite, sleep disturbances, and a reduction in vitality. These are the precursors of jet lag. The length of the journey may need several days for the body to revert to its previous condition and reestablish its original rhythm. Jet lag impacts people variably and manifests in diverse ways. The following elements contribute to this effect: a. Age, b. Prior sleep patterns, c. Introverted or extroverted disposition. The adaption time is contingent upon the flight's direction and length.

3. Height

It is well established that as altitude increases from sea level, air pressure decreases, resulting in a corresponding drop in the concentration of oxygen in the atmosphere. The human body acclimatizes to these circumstances by increasing the heart rate and respiratory rate. Hypoxia, resulting from insufficient oxygen for about twenty-one days, activates certain physiological systems and elevates hemoglobin levels in the bloodstream. Consequently, the heart rate and respiratory rate revert to their prior values owing to the elevated concentration of hemoglobin

in the bloodstream. This scenario offers a benefit when the athlete resumes normal levels for a certain duration, particularly in endurance-requiring conditions. Engaging in altitude training during a whole season yields no advantages. The organism that acclimatizes to altitude and elevates its hemoglobin levels during a three-week period reverts to its original condition and adjusts to sea level upon descent. The hemoglobin concentration reverts to its prior level. If just one match is to be conducted (some studies suggest it should occur during the first three or four days after descending to sea level; others propose within the first six or seven days), an advantage may be present. It is important to consider that such a mountain camp allows for the consolidation of all athletes, facilitates daily theoretical training in that discipline, and mitigates the effects of summer heat to some degree. Consequently, if the competition environment for an athlete or team is situated at high altitude, the aforementioned hazards are imminent. Consequently, it may be said that in sports disciplines where aerobic capacity is crucial, altitude poses a danger of performance decline if adequate adaptation is not achieved. In sectors with intensive anaerobic activity, a benefit arises due to the reduced air volume and thus less friction. Moreover, excessive loading at this stage may result in suboptimal performance owing to insufficient adaptation and may elevate the risk of damage.

4.Heat (Heat stroke)

Extremely hot environments where the body is not acclimatized (adapted to the climate) also pose a significant risk for athletes. This risk is “heat injuries.” Both the increase in the body’s internal temperature during exercise and the necessity of exercising in a hotter environment than the body is accustomed to can lead to certain disorders related to the increase in body temperature if the necessary precautions are not taken. The body’s heat regulation mechanism becoming incapable of responding to the needs due to internal (excessive exercise) and external (excessive heat) factors brings about the following problems, respectively:

1. Heat cramps: They occur as painful spasms, especially in the gastrocnemius muscle (calf muscle) that participates most intensively in exercise. This is basically due to a local electrolyte deficiency or fluid volume problem resulting from water and Na (sodium) loss in the working muscle.

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2. Heat fatigue: The feeling of extreme fatigue that occurs in hot environments can be relieved by rest and fluid intake.

3. Heat exhaustion: It occurs as fatigue, exhaustion, increased body temperature, dehydration (water loss), nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, headache, dizziness, loss of appetite, profuse sweating and muscle cramps. It is usually due to a decrease in blood volume. Exercise should be stopped immediately, rested in a shaded area, and electrolyte supplements should be given orally or intravenously with water.

4. Heat stroke: The most severe of the heat-related problems that occur as a result of excessive internal temperature. Behavioral disorders, emotional instability, hysterical crying, apathy, failure to respond to questions, loss of orientation in terms of time and place, involuntary defecation, dry hot skin, cessation of sweating, high rectal temperature, drop in blood pressure, sometimes low blood sugar, and finally loss of consciousness and circulatory collapse occur.

Heat-related injuries, which can pose a major health risk to athletes, can be prevented by:

1. The athlete must go through a good acclimatization period, that is, adaptation to the heat.
2. During training, frequent rests should be given in the shade. Appropriate amounts of water and salt should be given before, during and after exercise.
3. You should weigh yourself every day and any excessive weight loss in 24 hours should be taken into account.
4. Physical activity should be limited during periods of high heat and humidity.
5. Training hours should be preferred when the temperature is lower.
6. Athletes should choose light-colored clothing whenever possible.
7. The clothes preferred by athletes should allow the skin to breathe comfortably.

5.Cold

Frigid and blustery conditions pose a danger of sports injuries and diminish performance in athletic activities. Athletes may clearly have health issues, including colds. Furthermore, inadequate warming in this frigid environment results in numerous ailments. Cold conditions provide an atmosphere that heightens vulnerability to strain-related muscle injury. In such an environment, a decline in body temperature also decreases the body's oxygen consumption. Performance diminishes. In events and training conducted in such circumstances, heat-retaining apparel should be favored. This retention should be favored with cotton or woolen garments on the body. Wet garments should be avoided wherever feasible.

6.Dehydration

The depletion of water in the body is referred to as dehydration. Dehydration is classified into two categories: acute and chronic. The amount of water lost by perspiration during exercise varies based on the length, intensity, and ambient temperature of the activity. Failure to compensate for this water loss results in dehydration. This condition is referred to as acute dehydration. Prolonged water loss beyond 24 hours results in chronic dehydration.

7.Air pollution

Rising industrialization, substandard waste management resulting from urban migration, unregulated industrial growth without treatment facilities, and the daily influx of many automobiles contribute to air pollution in inhabited areas. Polluted air adversely impacts healthy individuals and disrupts the functions of the neuromuscular, cardiovascular, respiratory, and renal systems, despite its effects on the respiratory tract epithelium, increased mucosal secretion, and impaired ciliary movement in the trachea. It results in the collapse of the airway.

G. FACTORS RELATED TO HABITS

The athlete develops certain habits throughout his athletic career. Although the majority of these behaviors benefit him, several habits adversely impact the athlete. This section aims to enumerate the elements that jeopardize the athlete's health and adversely impact performance.

1. Alcohol

Alcohol is a drug that exhibits both stimulant and narcotic effects, contingent upon the quantity ingested. Alcohol is metabolized in the liver and converted into fat, exerting minimal influence on energy generation. It has a narcotic effect on the central nervous system contingent upon the dosage ingested. It impairs the athlete's focus. The immediate effects of alcohol impair response time, hand-eye coordination, balance, and complicated motor skills. It adversely impacts energy metabolism, maximum oxygen consumption, heart rate, stroke volume, muscle perfusion, and respiratory dynamics. It may diminish strength, power, endurance, and speed. Prolonged use may result in hepatic, cardiac, neurological, and muscular disorders, potentially culminating in mortality. Consequently, alcohol need to be regarded as a detrimental component that impairs athletic performance and heightens the chance of injury owing to subpar performance.

2. Smoking

The detrimental effects of smoking on human health are evident. Additionally, it adversely impacts athletic performance. In athletic endeavors where aerobic capacity is crucial, the detrimental impacts of smoking on performance are particularly evident. Nicotine in cigarettes diminishes the production of surfactant, a chemical that facilitates the complete inflation of lung alveoli. This diminishes the complete expansion of the alveoli and the rate of oxygen in the adjacent capillaries, so affecting the oxygen-carrying capacity. Athletes are inherently impacted by the detrimental effects of smoking on human health. Moreover, smoking adversely impacts their performance. Coaches undoubtedly provide their players with essential cautions about this

matter. They should exemplify appropriate behavior by refraining from smoking in the presence of athletes.

3.Nutrition

The athlete's dietary practices influence his performance. The athlete alone manages his dietary regimen outside of the training camps. Consequently, the dietary habits he develops should be grounded on sound principles of nutrition. The dietary habits, the composition of the last meal before to competition or training, and the beverages ingested during the event also influence athletic performance. The athlete's nutritional practices, misinformation, detrimental habits, dietary composition during strength training, timing of the final meal prior to competition or training, and the substances consumed before such events all influence athletic performance. A specialist should unequivocally be contacted about this matter.

4.Weight loss

A significant concern encountered in sports like wrestling, boxing, and judo, where weight classes are crucial, is fast weight loss. Athletes often disregard scientific approaches that need extended durations and habitually use weight reduction techniques acquired from their predecessors and peers. It is acknowledged that there are two origins of excess weight. Reducing body fat requires an extended duration, while the loss of bodily fluids may be achieved more readily by dehydration. Many athletes routinely engage in weight loss by limiting meal intake, reducing fluid consumption, and inducing perspiration by thermal means or without physical activity. The rationale for the selection is that acute dehydration (rapid weight loss) presents the following issues:

1. Decrease in muscle strength,
2. Decrease in work performance,
3. Decrease in plasma and blood volume,

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4. Decreased heart function during exercise, increased pulse rate, low stroke volume,
5. Especially in food restriction, decrease in oxygen use,
6. Decrease in heat regulation mechanisms
- 7.Reduction in renal blood flow and filtration
8. Decrease in liver glycogen storage
9. Increased electrolyte loss in the body

These reasons reduce the athlete's performance and increase the risk of injury.

5.Ergogenic aid

Ergogenic aids are some nutrients and methods used to increase performance. Genuine ergogenic aids are techniques that consistently enhance strength, endurance, speed, and skill. As they are not manmade compounds, they are not classified as doping. Athletes in the realm of sports use certain drugs alongside certain practices. These compounds often include brewer's yeast, pollen, and protein powders. Athletes use these medications based on anecdotal practices. Utilizing these medications without professional guidance may result in health complications and adversely impact performance. Ergogenic aids are foods and techniques used to enhance performance. Authentic ergogenic aids are techniques that consistently enhance strength, endurance, speed, and skill. As they are not manmade compounds, they are not classified as doping. Athletes in the realm of sports use certain drugs alongside certain practices. These compounds often include brewer's yeast, pollen, and protein powders. Athletes use these medications based on anecdotal practices. The use of these drugs without professional supervision may result in health complications and adversely impact performance.

6. Doping

Doping is a significant danger to athletes in its own right. In addition to undermining equitable competition in sports, its detrimental impact on human health is unequivocal. The detrimental impacts of doping on the human body were assessed via the lens of the automatic defense mechanism hypothesis, proposed by German scientists at a certain point in time. The doping chemicals used here activate reserves that the individual does not deliberately engage. The hypothesis of automatic defensive mechanisms posits that doping ingestion induces an unconscious and involuntary tension inside the body. This strain may have severe outcomes that may result in death, contingent upon the dosage consumed and the individual's resilience. A brief examination of the detrimental effects of doping substances on the human body, categorized by their groups in studies, reveals that the consumption of amphetamines leads to considerable economic loss due to the suppression of fatigue in the organism. The resting capacity diminishes considerably. It induces tachycardia, hypertension, hyperhidrosis, heightened muscular tone, anxiety, gastrointestinal disturbances, and impairment of sexual functioning. The use of anabolic drugs, often referred to as muscle builders, inflicts significant harm on the skeleton, liver, kidneys, and reproductive systems. Refer to Sports Science/Doping

7. Sexual life

In our mostly conservative culture, a significant topic that athletes are often uninformed of and that perpetually lingers as a question is sexuality. The understanding of athletes on this topic significantly differs based on the specific athletic discipline. In practice, several athletes get information on this topic via the guidance of their seasoned peers. Research indicates that the energy used during sexual intercourse is comparable to rapidly ascending many flights of stairs. The heart rate during sexual intercourse ranges from roughly 100 to 120 beats per minute. Providing enough recovery time post-coitus clearly prevents any physiological detriment. Furthermore, research indicates that engaging in sexual intercourse 24 hours before to and after the competition does not result in any physiological issues. Athletes maintain distinct sexual practices influenced by their respective sports and the societal ideals associated with those disciplines. Several hazards are present in this situation. Infectious

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infections that may occur in partnerships without adequate measures are a health concern for athletes. Another concern is the tensions arising from prolonged abstinence from sexual intercourse during the pre-competition period, which stems from some athletes seeing sexual activity as detrimental. In some athletes, particularly those who are single, sexual behavior may become reckless and ravenous. Here are two or three points: It induces diverse pressures and significant weariness in athletes, adversely impacting their performance.

8. Religious habits

Some athletes develop certain habits due to their religious beliefs. For instance, several professional sportsmen observe fasting throughout Ramadan. Prolonged fasting throughout the day inherently impacts an athlete's performance. It impairs the athlete's performance throughout training and competition. Moreover, diminished bodily resistance resulting from hunger renders the body susceptible to certain ailments. Some international athletes may also face the danger of underperformance on certain holy days. A significant number of American athletes choose not to compete or practice on Sundays. A like circumstance pertains to some Jewish sportsmen on Saturdays.

9. Sleep pattern

Alterations in the sleep patterns of some athletes (early bedtime, late bedtime, sleep disturbances) inherently influence their performance.

10. Changes in routine

Alterations in the athlete's established regimen may adversely affect him/her, contingent upon his/her constitution.

Conclusion

Sports have always been esteemed as a vehicle for personal development, physical conditioning, and collective solidarity. The quest for physical achievement sometimes entails considerable psychological and social costs. This study work seeks to examine the elements contributing to the obstacles encountered by athletes and the methods that may be used to alleviate these dangers. A key difficulty encountered by sports leaders is the fixation on evading failure instead of concentrating on the prerequisites for success (Wang et al., 2021). This fixation on danger may result in decision-making that favors risk aversion over audacious, inventive methods that might elevate an athlete or team to unprecedented levels. According to Fox et al., "Failure, in isolation, lacks significance and is inadequate for eliciting emotional reactions." The significance we assign to failure elicits emotional reactions" (Hanin, 2008). By comprehending the particular ramifications that athletes link to failure, such as shame, embarrassment, or the deterioration of significant relationships, sports psychologists and coaches can assist athletes in reframing their viewpoints and embracing the developmental prospects that arise from undertaking calculated risks. The fear of failing is a critical risk factor that may adversely impact an athlete's psychological health and performance. This dread may show as detrimental self-dialogue, worry, and an aversion to pursuing ambitious objectives. Researchers indicate that the fear of failure is often acquired during early socialization and may significantly impede sportsmen striving for the pinnacle of their sport. (Yıldırım et al., 2023) The repercussions of this dread of failure may be extensive, beyond the realm of athletics and impacting several facets of an athlete's life. Athletes experiencing elevated fear of failure may demonstrate behaviors such as self-blame, pessimism, and self-handicapping, which may diminish their resilience and extrinsic drive. Coaches and sports psychologists must exert considerable effort to assist players in surmounting this anxiety and fostering a more constructive, growth-oriented mentality.

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